

DAILY LIFE OF CITY DWELLERS IN KARAKALPAKSTAN DURING THE WORLD WAR II THE WORLD WAR II

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Abstract. This article is about the issues of everyday life of the urban population of Karakalpakstan in the period of beginning of World War II. Particular attention is paid to the living conditions of the residents of the city of Nukus - the capital of the republic, where on the eve of the war the republican management and management bodies moved. The construction of the city continued, which led to the rapid growth of the city's population on the eve of the war. An analysis of archival documents and materials shows that during the Second World War, there were serious changes in the daily life of all segments of the population. It is indicated that the beginning of the Second World War brought new rules of life and work to the life of the townspeople. Labor discipline has intensified, there have been changes in the provision of food to the cities, and the time for rest and leisure of citizens has been reduced. The harsh everyday life of the war has influenced both the consciousness of people and their patriotic mood. Because of the difficult military situation, there was a reduction in food and industrial state funds, which affected the provision of citizens with goods of mass demand.

Keywords: World War II, everyday life of the urban population, Karakalpakstan, the city of Chimbay, Khojeyli, Nukus, the urban population, the military-economic plan, bread, martial law, production of goods and food

The war against fascism is an important event in the life of Uzbek people, like all the peoples of the Soviet Union. The interest of all mankind in this terrible war, which claimed the lives of tens of millions of people, has not weakened for years, but continues to grow, for it is a fateful, integral phenomenon in the history and historiography of the former republics of the USSR, already independent states. The people of Karakalpakstan made a certain contribution to the victory over fascism in World War II, along with other peoples of the Soviet Union. Envoys from Karakalpakstan fought bravely and selflessly on the war fronts, while old men, women and adolescents worked tirelessly in the rear.

The study and generalization of the history of the Second World War has a scientific, theoretical and practical significance and continues to be one of the topical areas of research in historical science today. In the historiography of Karakalpakstan, this topic had its own researchers. But at the same time, these works have a historical-party character, so the researchers expressed a certain point of view within the framework of the official concept of war. For example, the main research topics related to the years of World War II and the role of Karakalpakstan in it concerned the activities of the party, komsomol and trade union organizations, the public and labor collectives in the implementation of specific directions of the "wartime" policy, heroism and patriotism of ordinary people who fought on the fronts and worked in the rear. The shortcomings, contradictions, costs and negative consequences of the war were not lighted up at all in the historiography of Karakalpakstan.

According to the 1939 census, 476 thousand people lived in Karakalpakstan, of which 58 thousand were the urban population [1]. That time the capital of the republic - the city of Nukus, numbered about 10 thousand people [2]. The average natural population growth in 1941 was 5,622 people, however, according to archival documents, "the numbers are relatively far from accurate, even in cities, not all of the dead are registered, and few people care about the registration of the dead in rural areas" [3].

The largest traditional cities were Turtkul, Chimbay, Khojeyli and Kungrad. The main production capacity of the republic was concentrated in Turtkul, however, at the end of 1939 - beginning of 1940, most of the state institutions and departments moved to Nukus. In the same year, the construction of a nursery, a state bank, a post office, a hotel, residential buildings and other facilities was completed. In 1940, the buildings of the radio center, the prosecutor's office, the post office were erected, telephone communications were being established. The construction of a furniture factory, a brewery, as well as a polygraphic plant began, which went into operation in 1940 [4].

Nukus was still under construction, labor was required for construction, so people from all regions of the republic came to the capital. In a short time, the population of the city increased to 14 thousand people. The social infrastructure of Nukus was not yet ready for such a rapid influx of population. Indeed, by that time, many social facilities had not been completed yet, the improvement of the city was at the initial stage. In the 1940 budget, special attention is paid to health care, public education, improvement of cities and regional centers, cultural and everyday events.

Particular attention was paid to the creation of favorable living conditions for the townspeople, since there were special, difficult natural and climatic conditions in Nukus: continuous winds and dust created great trouble for the townspeople. Chairman of the Executive Committee of the Nukus City Council V.M. Baryl'nikov, speaking at the third session of the Supreme Council of the Karakalpak ASSR (May 25-27, 1940), gives an interesting picture of the city of that period: "between the new and the old city on an area of 280 hectares stretches a sandy wasteland (this is today's area of the central market, the amphitheater and north of these objects - author's note), from here sands and dust are carried to the city. It is necessary to irrigate this area as soon as possible, to develop it for the construction of residential buildings and a park, as well as the creation of a protective green zone" [5].

In March 1941, the Council of People's Commissars of the republic adopted a resolution "On the improvement of the city of Nukus", according to which it was planned to plant 50 thousand tree plantations, the so-called "green belt" and greening of city streets. In the spring of the same year, over 95,000 tall trees and bushes were planted. The survival rate was about 90%, however, their watering was poorly organized. Through the efforts of the organization and the residents themselves, they began to dig irrigation ditches along the streets, which received water from small canals. There were several of them, originating from Kyzketken. For example, one of them was dug in the area of today's Central Market through the center of the new city (on the right bank of the Kyzketken). This made it possible to sow about 250 hectares of urban and suburban areas with vegetable and melon crops and garden and grape plantations. However, the improvement and public services of the townspeople lagged behind the construction work, for which the chairman of the Nukus city executive committee Baryl'nikov was reprimanded in July 1941 [6].

With the outbreak of war, the entire economy of the republic was rebuilt to meet the needs of the front. Tough discipline was established in enterprises, industrial artels and other industries. In July 1941, the Council of People's Commissars of the republic and the Karakalpak regional committee of the CP (Committee Party)(b) Uzb "On the general compulsory preparation of the population for air and chemical defense" was adopted [7]. For this, members of OSOAVIAKHIM (Society for the Promotion of Defense, Aviation and Chemical Engineering), a paramilitary voluntary society, were involved, as well as to organize training courses for instructors and begin training the entire population according to the compiled 13-hour program. All citizens of the republic from 16 to 45 years old were covered by universal education, and in the cities classes began on October 1, 1941. In cities and districts, it was also proposed to organize self-defense groups of women activists, old people and adolescents, that is, people of non-military age.

The second task was to teach the Russian language to pre-conscripts and to eliminate illiteracy among the adult population. On September 30, 1941, a special resolution of the Council of People's Commissars of Karakalpakstan was adopted on this issue, according to which it was planned to attract 4491 townspeople and 33,013 rural residents for teaching the Russian language, teach the alphabet and writing in Cyrillic. From November 1, 1941, the departments of public education were to begin teaching literacy and the Russian language to 325 recruits born in 1923 and 1924, 743 illiterate and 2663 people who do not speak Russian [8].

The next task is to release products for the needs of the front. The Council of People's Commissars of the republic, headed by P. Seitov, outlined the expansion of the production of goods and food through the use of local raw materials: wild (kendyr, dzhida, reeds), wool and leather, other raw materials of animal husbandry (horns, hooves, bones), open minerals (salt, copper, gypsum, clay), fish. Local industrial cooperation began to widely use local raw materials, for example, for the production of a wagon train from local tree species, carts, cart, began to produce soap, fish sausages, salted vegetables, dried melons, and also to make cotton yarns. This became possible due to the enlargement of artels: at the beginning of the war in the republic there were 26 artels with 2965 workers, by the end of 1941 there were 18 of them with 29888 people [9].

The urban population was the first to feel the power of government decisions. On August 16, 1941, the Council of People's Commissars of the USSR and the Central Committee of the All-Union Communist Party (b) approved the military-economic plan presented by the State Planning Committee for the fourth quarter of 1941 and for 1942 for the regions of the Volga region, the Urals, Western Siberia, Kazakhstan and Central Asia, which was put into effect literally in for several days, which significantly reduced the "gap" in the transition from a peaceful state to a military one [10].

As Pirzhan Seitov and Nauryz Zhapakov testify, the role of the upper echelons of management has increased. The mechanism of concrete, detailed leadership, fine-tuned even before the war, began to operate with even greater tension. The system of delegates has become widespread. In the villages and rural areas, emergency bodies were again created - the political departments of the MTS (Machine-Tractor Station) and state farms. Militarization provided for the unconditional fulfillment of the order-plan, disciplinary responsibility for its violation, and the introduction, if necessary, of a barracks regime. From November 17, 1941, in all the people's commissariats, central, city and regional institutions, as well as in public,

trade union and cooperative organizations, working hours were set from 9 to 17.30 with a half-hour break [11]. At the same time, a special form of food supply (bread, sugar, confectionery) was established for the nomenclature. So, according to the resolution of the Council of People's Commissars of the republic "On the supply of leading Soviet and party workers with bread, sugar, confectionery" dated November 17, 1941, executives of categories 1 and 2 were issued special food cards [12].

The beginning of the war made its own adjustments in the life of the citizens of Karakalpakstan. Labor discipline has intensified, changes have taken place in the provision of food to cities, and the time for rest and leisure of citizens has been reduced. P. Seitov argued that at that moment it was important to rely not only on the mobilization approach necessary in extreme conditions, but also on the psychology of the working person himself, on the political, social, moral motives of his behavior, on his striving in deed, and not in words. not by vows, not by an instant impulse of the soul, to express their patriotism [13]. This is on the one hand, but on the other hand, the living conditions in the city began to gradually deteriorate. So, at the beginning of 1941 in Nukus, 80 farms were allocated plots for the construction of individual housing, at the beginning of July only 12 managed to finish construction, the rest did not have time with the transition of the economy to martial law. Problems began with the provision of bread products: on September 30, 1941, the Council of People's Commissars of the republic specially considered the issue "About the state of bread baking and grain trade in the city of Nukus" [14], which indicates interruptions in the quality and delivery of bread. In general, at the beginning of the war, the urban population of the republic felt more acutely the hardships of wartime, they began to feel difficulties with food everywhere and needed better housing conditions.

References:

1. Public economy of the Karakalpak ASSR for 60 years. - N., 1984. - S.5.
2. The national economy of the USSR. 1922-1972. Jubilee statistic yearbook. - M., 1972. - S.25.
3. Central State Archives of the RK, f. 273, op.1, d.122, l.58.
4. Nukus, the capital of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, is an ancient and modern city. - T., 2002. - P.29.
5. The third session of the Supreme Soviet of the Karakalpak ASSR. May 25-27, 1940 - N., 1941. - S.69-71.
6. Central State Archives of the RK, f. R-322, op.1, d.802, l.30.
7. Central State Archives of the RK, f. R-322, op.1, d.802, l.106.
8. Central State Archives of the RK, f. R-322, op.1, d.817, l.47.
9. Central State Archives of the RUz, f.2325, op.1, d.423, l.26.
10. Olshanskiy A., Arzymbetov United family in battles for the Motherland. Nukus. 1981. - S.34.
11. Central State Archives of the RK, R-322, op.1, d.796, l.74.
12. Central State Archives of the RK, R-322, op.1, d.796, l.61.
13. Seitov P. Highway// Soviet Karakalpakstan. 1984. 15 November.
14. Central State Archives of the RK, f.R-322, op.1, d.801, l. 186.